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The model of perceptual quality on private brands: Application of text analysis

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Abstract

This study takes the customers of RT-Mart, Auchan and Wal-Mart as the research objects, and explores the influence of product type on consumers' perception of private brand products. A total of 30 customers were interviewed and researched. The methodology adopted the application of text analysis, and the data analysis was carried out with grounded theory. The context is summarized, and the insights of theoretical propositions are put forward. Finally, The Model of Perceptual Quality on Private Brands is established, which provides academic reference indicators and the direction for managers to operate well.

Keywords: Private Branding; Perceived Quality; Text Analysis; Grounded Theory, Theoretical Propositions

1. Introduction

The competitive feature of mass-market stores is price (1). In order to provide cheaper products than competitors and maintain customer loyalty, mass-market stores expect suppliers to cooperate with promotions and price reductions, but suppliers are usually reluctant to cut own profit. Therefore, mass retailers develop their own private brand products and allow themselves to control product prices.

In recent years, the mass sales industry has also developed a trend of developing private brand products. At the same time, due to the improvement of knowledge and culture and the rise of consumers' quality awareness, customers are increasingly accepting private brand products from well-known distributors. However, the promotion of private brand products is fast or slow. It depends on the marketing strategy and promotion of distributors (1).

In recent years, mass retailers have launched private brand products, including the ARO products launched by Makro, the Big Thumb LOGO of RT-Mart, the Carrefour LOGO, FIRST LINE LOGO and other series. What kind of guidelines do mass retailers have in the development of private brand products? From the perspective of consumers, what kind of products are more suitable for private brand development? This is the first question of this study. In addition, what kind of private brand products should mass retailers advertise to consumers? As a basis for purchase, this is the second question of this study. In addition, because consumers feel different degrees of relevance to something based on their own needs, values, and interests, they also have different degrees of involvement in the thing (2), so the purpose of this study is (1) Put forward a theoretical proposition on the perceived quality of private brands; (2) establish a model of perceived quality of private brands.

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2. Literature Review

2.1. Related private brand research

(3) defines three types of product brands in the retail industry: (1) manufacturer brands, known as nation brands, which are produced and distributed by manufacturers and widely used by consumers. (2) house brands or private brands, which are specially developed for sale in retail stores; (3) generics, also known as no-name brands, that is, there is no brand name on the product (8; 9). (5) discussed the influencing factors of the market share of private brands, using the sales database of chain supermarkets to analyze and summarize three dimensions, namely the quality and stability dimension, the intermediary profit dimension, the manufacturer Competitive dimension (11; 22). (4) research pointed out that the cognitive quality and price gap between private brand and manufacturer brand is getting smaller and smaller. As a result, the results of many studies on private brands will vary over time, product type, and location.

(6) first proposed Preference Goods, which believed that when consumers buy preference goods, they only have low purchasing effort and low self-involvement, but they have high brand preference (9; 13; 18). (7) explained four types of consumer goods in terms of purchasing effort and perceived risk. Convenience products: The level of effort and risk is the lowest, and consumers will not spend too much money and time on purchasing convenience products, and they will not perceive significant risks when making choices. Preference goods: The degree of effort and risk are higher, and the main difference between them and convenience goods is the perceived risk of buyers. Often consumers' perceived risk is heightened through marketing efforts in branding and advertising (eg. consumers' preference for Coca-Cola's taste and image is attracted by advertising or brand preference) (8; 13; 16). Purchases: Consumers are willing to spend a lot of time and money in finding and evaluating purchases, and consumers have increased perceived risk to such high-involvement products. Special products: consumers have the highest level of effort and perceived risk, and the main difference between them and purchases is effort rather than perceived risk. Consumers will be willing to look everywhere, it's okay to wait a while to get a product, and they won't accept other substitutes (25; 33; 40).

The above definition shows (41) that the classification of consumer goods is highly correlated with product involvement and perceived risks. Therefore, based on the different priorities consumers consider when purchasing, the cost and willingness to be invested in purchasing are different (33; 39; 42). The degree of risk exposure and perceived risk varies, so consumers will have different perceived quality of different types of consumer products when purchasing products.

(8) believe that dividing consumer goods into convenience goods, preference goods, optional goods and special goods is the effort and risk invested in purchasing products. However, effort and risk are highly interdependent dimensions, which can be replaced by the level of involvement of buyers. Convenience and preference products are low-involvement products, while optional and special products are high-involvement products. Consumers will have different perceived risks for different product types, and the more detailed and complete the functional description of the product, the less uncertain the perceived product function will be (20; 29; 40; 43).

Scholars have done a lot of research on the processing mode of consumers after receiving the information (29). The most famous processing mode is the information processing mode developed by (9; 32; 34). It believes that consumers will go through five basic steps of exposure, attention, comprehension, acceptance, and retention after a stimulus such as an advertising message appears, the stimulation of information must enter the above five steps to achieve memory, but because the involvement of consumers themselves (involvement) is different, so each consumer's degree of processing information is different. The degree of involvement affects every step of information processing. Therefore, the factors affecting the information processing mode may come from individuals or from the information itself, but in general, the degree of involvement of the information on the consumer itself varies (21; 33; 41).

The concept of involvement was proposed by Krugman in 1965 when he studied advertising. Since then, the discussion of involvement has gradually become one of the mainstream of consumer behavior research. Because each scholar has different definitions and measurement methods for consumers involved in different objects. This study refers to the research of (10; 27; 29) to conduct literature research. According to the results and structure of its induction, there are three degrees of involvement of consumers, which can be divided into: (1) Involvement with advertisement (involvement with advertisement), (2) involvement with product, (3) involvement with purchase, so-called product involvement means that consumers may pay attention to different products or brands. Due to the differences in attributes provided, different consumers will have different levels of attention or personal subjective awareness of products or brands (19; 26; 28). If consumers have a high degree of involvement in a certain type of product, the behavior displayed is to perceive that this type of product is more important and will perceive the difference between brands (8; 11; 21).

2.2. Related perceptual quality research

(11) defined perceptual quality as consumers consciously or unconsciously processing some cues related to quality attributes under meaningful personal or situational variables, thereby affecting their choice of the most suitable products for consumption. This special value judgment is for perceptual quality. (12) believes that in a broad sense, quality can be defined as the superiority of a product; further, perceived quality can be defined as "consumers' judgment on the overall superiority of a product". The following is the definition of "perceived quality" by various scholars in this research (8; 32; 36).

(13) distinguish four value dimensions—preference, product-subject interaction, relativity, and consumer experience; these value dimensions provide a conceptual framework for the definition of perceived quality: (1) Perceived quality is an evaluative preference or judgment. Perceived quality is a variable with a continuous band, rather than a dichotomous variable (14; 16). It is a comprehensive judgment based on quality attributes; (2) Perceived quality is the result of the interaction between a product and consumers (13; 19). Quality judgment is formed by individual consumers for a specific product, which means that the quality of a product may be very different among different consumers; (3) Perceived quality is a relative concept (15; 22).

Perceptual quality is comparative, individual and situational, so it is a relative concept (21; 23). The perceived quality of a product may be affected by other competing products, the number of alternative product alternatives may also affect the evaluation process for a particular product alternative, and quality judgments may vary among individual consumers due to prior use experience, education level, perceived risk varies. In addition, perceptual quality will be affected by situational variables, such as the use target of the purchased product, physical environment, time pressure, social background environment and other factors; (4) The consumption experience of the product. Consumption refers not only to actual use, but also to owning and appreciating a product. Therefore, consumer experience affects the cognitive process of product quality (30; 36; 41).

(14) believes that the perceived quality is different from the actual quality mainly for the following reasons: (1) Consumers' previous impressions will affect their judgment of quality. Consumers will be affected by the previous impression of poor quality, making them no longer believe in the new demands of the product, and even unwilling to take the time to confirm whether the quality of the product has been improved (6; 24; 29); The perception of the importance of face is different. Although the company achieves the quality goal of a certain aspect, consumers may not consider this aspect to be an important item; (3) the information obtained by consumers is incomplete.

From the above literature, it can be inferred that product information will have a positive impact on perceived quality. According to the above relationship, it should also be applicable to private brands (9; 11; 34).

(15) found that social risk (social risk) can hinder consumers from purchasing private brands in certain usage situations (self-use or gift-giving). (16) studied the determinants of consumers' purchase of private brands and found that when the product is detectable, that is, the main ingredients of the product are directly used, it will increase the purchase intention of private brands. Such as sugar, rice, noodles, etc., consumers are highly receptive to this type of private brand developed by retailers, because consumers believe that it has no difference in quality and ingredients except for the packaging and the manufacturer's brand (19; 22. 34; 44).

(17) pointed out that the higher the familiarity with private brands, the lower the perceived risk of buying private brands, and the more willing consumers are to buy private brands. (18) proposed that consumers are exposed to different risks when purchasing and consuming. These risks can be divided into three categories as follows: functional risks, financial risks, and social risks. These three risks may have alternative effects. Private brands are attractive because their lower prices eliminate financial risk (16 19); however, if consumers choose to buy a manufacturer's brand, they are willing to sacrifice financial risk to reduce functional risk and social risks. The functional risk referred to here is the complexity of the product category, the variation in category quality, and the average purchase time (20; 31; 34).

(19) believes that the complexity of product categories is negatively correlated with the perceived quality of private-label products, because products with more complex manufacturing processes tend to have higher defect rates. Therefore, this study believes that the complexity of product types has an impact on the perceived quality and perceived risk of private brand consumers. The manufacturing complexity of convenience products is often lower than that of purchased products (11; 13). Therefore, in terms of private brands, convenience products and preference products The perceived quality of the product will be higher than that of the purchased product (23; 31).

(20) pointed out that the information processing method of high-involvement consumers is mainly the central route, which has sufficient motivation to process the information obtained. For this type of consumers, comparative advertising (comparative advertising) focuses on product attributes, scientific evidence and other information in the content, which can trigger their information processing motivation, and then internalize the information into part of the personal memory to achieve the memory effect (16; 27); on the contrary, low-involvement consumers. The information processing process is relatively simple, and the motivation for processing information is weaker, and the information provided by comparative advertising is richer and less able to attract the attention of consumers (18; 31; 40). The intensity of information in advertisements has a positive and significant impact on brand attitude and purchase intention; the stronger the information intensity, the better the brand attitude and the higher the purchase intention, and high involvement is more significant than low involvement (22; 35). The richer the information of private brand products in advertisements, the more significant consumers have a positive impact on the brand equity and purchase intention of private brands. Because one of the dimensions of brand equity is perceived quality, the above relationship should also be applicable to private brand products. perceptual quality (7. 16; 28).

3. Research Method

3.1. Text analysis

In this study, text analysis was used to decode cases (12; 22). Text analysis methodology combines the advantages of in-depth interviews, participant observation, and content analysis (22; 23; 24; 25; 26), especially in data analysis. The rigor is to use the qualitative analysis software of Nvivo 12 to carry out four-stage coding and decoding analysis. It is superior to the superior properties of content analysis alone (27). With its theoretical development of systematically collecting and analyzing data, through scientific principles, comparative principles and the use of systematic procedures, it develops and inductively guides the theory of texts from real data for a certain phenomenon. (22) pointed out that its connotation is a delicate method of systematically and intensively analyzing data, usually word-by-word or line by line analysis of fieldwork records, interview records, or other Documents, as well as frequent comparisons, extensive collection of data and entries to produce a well-constructed theory (27; 28).

The purpose of this study using textual analysis is to obtain the textual meaning of the perceived quality of private brands (28; 29; 30; 31). Text analysis is not about proposing a theory and then testing it; it is about determining a field of study and then generating concepts from that field (22; 26; 29). If a concept faithfully reflects the daily life of a substantive area and is carefully derived from a variety of sources, then the concept should be able to describe the area very well. The focus of analysis is not only on collecting and arranging data. Combination is the organization of many emerging concepts from the analyzed data (24; 27; 32).

After establishing the research topic and policy, this study quickly entered the field, and conducted extensive collection of literature and field data to improve theoretical sensitivity (22; 34; 41). Theoretical sensitivity is based on the researcher's personal characteristics, a method that can detect the subtle meaning of field data, remove the trivial data, identify what is important and what is not, and can give important parts of meaning. Ability, which can also be called text literacy (24; 25; 26). In a narrow sense, it refers to the ability to read and write; in a broad sense, it also includes the researcher's personal ability to teach and the skills of professional skills in text analysis methodology. With the ability of textual literacy, researchers can examine the situation and related data from a new perspective, and can also deeply explore the unknown tacit knowledge part of field data for the development of theory (22).

Theoretical sensitivity is one of the most important concepts in text analysis research. The broad meaning of theoretical sensitivity includes the ability of researchers to perceive the connotation and meaning of data. This ability comes from literature, professional experience, and personal experience. In addition, the analysis of the data during the researcher's research can also improve the researcher's theoretical sense (27). In order to apply the theoretical touch of this research, the interviewees first understand the content and meaning of the discussion, collect data through the interview process, and then carry out data analysis, coding method, contextualization, and inductive text concepts on a line-by-line basis.

(24) pointed out in the applied research of grounded hermeneutics that the sample of text analysis research must be able to provide "depth" and "the breadth of multiple social facts" as the value standard, rather than quantitative research that can. The sample representing the population and inferring to the parent group of the population is the sampling principle (27; 28); the sample for quantitative research focuses on representativeness, tending to the random nature of the sample and the number required for statistical inference; Sexuality research pays attention to the richness of sample information, and tends to start from the perspective of previous experience and theory, and theoretical understanding is often the first step in selecting samples (22; 42).

Research object

The research object takes the customers of RT-Mart, Auchan and Wal-Mart as the research objects to explore the influence of product type on consumers' perceived quality of private brand products. A total of 30 customers were interviewed and researched, and the codes were M01, M02, F03, F04, M05, F06, M07, F08, F09, F10, F11, F12, M13, F14, F15, F16, F17, M18, F19, F20 F21, F22, F23, M24, F25, F26, F27, F28, F29, F30 (F for female, M for male). A total of 30 respondents were interviewed. Using semi-structured field interviews and audio recordings, and writing verbatim transcripts, the conceptualization of data, the establishment of categories, and the contextualization of field data texts (24; 25).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. The model of perceptual quality of private label on grounded theory

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the impact on perceived quality of private brands. The influence of product type on perceived quality of private brand products and the influence of perceived quality of private brand products on their purchase intention. The Model of Perceptual Quality on Private Label is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The Model of Perceptual Quality on Private Brands

4.2. Propositions

Figure 1 is explained below. Many scholars believe that qualitative research can construct substantive theories (22; 23; 24; 25; 28), and text analysis is a very useful method (22; 28; 29; 32; 33). This research uses textual analysis to construct substantive theories and models, as well as propositional methods for better interpretation and understanding.

(34) proposed that the complexity of product categories is negatively correlated with the perceived quality of private-label products, because products with more complex manufacturing processes tend to have higher defect rates.

Through in-depth interviews and field observations, this study found that the complexity of product types has an effect on the perceived quality and perceived risk of private brand consumers, and the manufacturing complexity of convenience products is often lower than that of purchased products.

According to in-depth interviews, it is also found that, for private brands, the perceived quality of convenience and preferred products is higher than that of shopping. According to the above research conclusions of the in-depth interviews, the following propositions can be made.

- **Proposition 1:** The higher the complexity of the private brand product, the higher the perceived quality.

- **Proposition 2:** The higher the product complexity of a private label product, the higher the perceived risk.
- **Proposition 3:** The richer the product information of the private brand, the higher the perceived quality.

Scholars such as (35) believe that explicit attribute cues include brand name and store name, and further influence perceived quality, perceived value and purchase intention. The relationship between product attributes, price and purchase intention is affected by many mediating factors, including perceived price, perceived quality, and perceived value, and perceived quality is positively affected by perceived price and essential attribute information (36; 43).

Through in-depth interviews and field observations, this research found that the perceived quality is affected by the essential attributes of the product. When more product information is provided, the higher the information value, the higher the consumer's perceived quality of the product.

According to in-depth interviews, it is also found that when explicit attribute information (brand name, store name) exists, it has a greater impact on the perceived quality of the product. According to the above research conclusions, the following propositions can be made.

- **Proposition 4:** The higher the information value, the higher the consumer's perceived quality of the product.
- **Proposition 5:** When explicit attribute information (brand name, store name) is present, the perceived quality of the product is more influential.

The information processing model developed by (37) in which information stimuli must enter the five steps of stimulation, exposure, attention, understanding, and acceptance to achieve memory, but because consumers have different degrees of involvement in products, that is, It is said that each consumer has a different ability to understand information processing, so the degree of consumer processing information is different, and the degree of involvement affects every step of information processing. Taking this step of understanding as an example, when consumers are more involved in information, consumers have a higher understanding of information, so consumers are more receptive to the product information (38; 44).

(20) found that the intensity of information in advertising has a positive and significant impact on brand attitudes and purchase intentions; the stronger the information intensity, the better the brand attitude, the higher the purchase intention, and the higher the level of involvement than the lower the level of involvement. more pronounced. From the above discussion on the degree of product involvement, it can be seen that the degree of product involvement will interfere with the impact of advertising information on brand equity. Product information can be regarded as the effect of advertising information, and one of the dimensions of brand equity is perceived quality, from the above, it can be inferred that the degree of product involvement in the impact of product information on perceived quality will have a disturbing effect (39). The influencing factors of information processing may come from individuals or from the information itself. If consumers are high-involvement consumers of products, their degree of involvement in information is relatively high, but in general, it is the degree of involvement of consumers themselves. The level of information processing motivation will have an impact.

Through in-depth interviews and field observations, this study found that the higher consumers' perception of product quality, the higher their perceived value of the product, and the higher the perceived value of the product will also increase consumers' willingness to purchase the product. In other words, consumers' perceived quality of products will affect their willingness to purchase products. The above relationship should also be applicable to private brands.

According to in-depth interviews, it is also found that when the level of involvement of consumers is low, the more product information, the greater the perceived quality of private brand products; The greater the amount of information, the limited degree of increase in the perceived quality of the product. Hence the following proposition.

- **Proposition 6:** The higher the consumer's perceived quality of the private brand, the higher the purchase intention.
- **Proposition 7:** The higher the consumer's perceived quality of a private brand, the higher the perceived value.
- **Proposition 8:** The higher the consumer's perceived value, the higher the purchase intention

5. Conclusion

The mass merchandiser mainly emphasizes a wide variety of commodities, high quality and low price, to meet the basic requirements of consumers in their daily lives. After ten years of development, there are more than 100 mass-selling

stores in China. There are many chain brands and the competition is becoming more and fiercer. In addition to facing price competition among the same industry, the industry must also compete with department stores that demand service, and provide complete and selective products. Most of the theme stores, and convenience stores, supermarkets, etc. compete with each other.

In the face of a strong market for foreign and international mass retailers, the industry is actively reducing the price, improving the quality of the shopping environment and expanding the functions of the competition. Small and medium-sized local mass retailers who lack the ability to integrate corporate management may inevitably be eliminated in the future. Fate.

Large-scale international chains and local companies are competing to join the domestic battlefield. Although the total turnover has increased year by year, most of them are due to the effect of newly opened stores. The existing old stores are still affected by the overall prosperity and the increase in market density. Is the most important.

Therefore, in addition to adopting price competition policies, industry players should strengthen the integration of procurement and marketing systems, strengthen logistics and warehousing functions, improve procurement bargaining power, and reduce marketing costs. Price strategy; at the same time, applying information technology, strengthening the provision of information-based products and services, and enhancing differentiated characteristics, can we seek development in competition and breakthroughs in growth.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this manuscript article.

Statement of informed consent

The author has the consent of the case study establishment for the survey, interview and the respondents data collected in the study area.

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